

THE DYNAMICS OF NETIZENS' PERCEPTIONS TOWARD JENNIFER COPPEN'S PERSONAL BRANDING ON TIKTOK

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Abstract. This study examines the dynamics of netizens' perceptions toward Jennifer Coppen's personal branding on TikTok across various phases of her personal life that attracted public attention. The study aims to understand how public perception is formed, negotiated, and transformed through digital interactions within the algorithmic environment of social media. This research employed a qualitative method with a narrative analysis approach by analyzing netizens' comments on Jennifer Coppen's TikTok account from May 2023 to August 2025. The research data consisted of nine TikTok posts and 72 netizen comments selected purposively and categorized into criticism, hate comments, disappointment, empathy, appreciation, and support. Data analysis was conducted using Stuart Hall's reception theory and Peter Montoya's *Eight Laws of Personal Branding* concept. The findings indicate that netizens' perceptions of Jennifer Coppen's personal branding are dynamic and influenced by social values, emotional engagement, and the consistency of the image presented on social media. During the phase of pregnancy before marriage, netizens' responses were dominated by criticism and moral judgment. In the phase of family life and mourning, public perception shifted toward empathy, support, and appreciation of Jennifer as a resilient mother figure. However, when Jennifer introduced a new partner, public perception once again generated criticism and disappointment because netizens associated the action with narratives she had previously conveyed. This study concludes that personal branding on TikTok is not entirely controlled by public figures, but is continuously negotiated through audience reception, emotional attachment, and collective narratives within the digital sphere.

Keywords: personal branding, TikTok, netizens' perception, audience reception, digital narrative.

INTRODUCTION

Public perception of public figures on TikTok is formed rapidly and dynamically through user interactions and algorithmic mechanisms that continuously reinforce the flow of digital conversations. TikTok functions not only as a medium of entertainment and information consumption, but also as a space for digital identity formation and personal branding, where the image of public figures can be collectively negotiated. The characteristics of TikTok's algorithm, which prioritize interaction, emotion, and audience engagement, make public opinion highly fluid and difficult to be fully controlled by the public figures themselves. This condition demonstrates that personal branding on TikTok is not merely an individual communication strategy, but rather the result of complex interactions among public figures, audiences, and the platform's algorithmic system.

Figure 1. Jennifer Coppen's TikTok Account (@jennifer.coppen)

(Source: <https://www.TikTok.com/@jennifer.coppen>)

Jennifer Coppen's digital journey illustrates the dynamics of public image formation that evolved alongside the changes in life phases she displayed on social media. Jennifer Coppen is a public figure recognized through the entertainment industry and actively shares her personal life on social media, particularly TikTok. Her account has a large number of followers and a high level of interaction, making every uploaded post capable of generating widespread responses from netizens. Jennifer's digital activities not only contain entertainment content but also document personal life phases openly presented to the public. This condition makes Jennifer a relevant subject for observing the dynamics of changes in netizens' perceptions toward the personal branding of public figures in the digital sphere.

Jennifer's digital journey reflects the dynamics of public image formation that developed in line with the transformation of her life phases. The first phase that attracted significant public attention occurred when she openly announced her pregnancy before marriage. The disclosure triggered waves of hate comments and moral stigma from some netizens. Pregnancy outside marriage was considered contradictory to religious values and social norms embraced by certain segments of society (Awalia, 2023). In this phase, Jennifer's identity was shaped not only by what

she presented, but also by the audience's collective judgment based on particular moral frameworks. The resulting image tended to be negative and vulnerable to distortion of meaning due to the dominance of judgmental opinions.

In the following phase, public narratives gradually shifted when Jennifer embraced her role as a mother and later built a family life. Her marriage, which took place after the birth of her child, was interpreted by part of the audience as a form of responsibility and commitment (Astuti & Berlian, 2023). Gradually, Jennifer's image experienced restoration. She began to be perceived as a more mature and warm mother and wife figure. The family-oriented content she shared created an image of emotional stability and personal closeness that made her appear more relatable. In addition to being recognized as a public figure, Jennifer had also established a beauty business, Jennskin Naturals, since 2020, which further strengthened her image as an independent and productive young woman (Rahmawati, 2024).

The transformation of her image became even stronger when Jennifer faced the loss of her life partner. The mourning phase became an important turning point in shaping public empathy. Posts portraying her grieving process and struggles as a single mother invited sympathy and emotional support from netizens. During this period, Jennifer was perceived as a strong and resilient figure in confronting personal trauma (Arliprayanda, 2024). She also demonstrated productivity by developing business activities, including her involvement in the Chewy's Dessert business alongside her sister-in-law, Zoe Wassink, in 2024 (Nabilla, 2025). This step further reinforced her personal branding as a resilient woman capable of rising amid difficult circumstances. Public perception during this phase was dominated by empathy, support, and appreciation.

However, the dynamics of public perception changed significantly again when Jennifer introduced a new partner to the public sphere. This decision triggered waves of criticism and hate comments from some netizens who considered the timing too soon after her mourning period. Public perception, which had previously been dominated by empathy, shifted into moral debates regarding propriety and what was considered the ideal timing to begin a new relationship. Public opinion became divided into supporting and opposing groups (Pijar, 2025).

The supporting group believed that Jennifer had the right to continue her life and build new happiness after enduring a period of loss. In contrast, the opposing group viewed the decision as a form of insensitivity toward the mourning period. The changing responses indicate how social expectations toward women figures and single mothers tend to be inflexible. Interactions within the comment sections demonstrate how netizens compare each phase of life, evaluate the consistency of the image presented, and construct moral narratives based on their respective perspectives.

The transition from a phase of empathy to the re-emergence of hate comments demonstrates that Jennifer Coppen's personal branding is fluctuating and continuously negotiated by audiences. The image built through narratives of resilience and independence can shift when the public interprets new events through different value frameworks. This phenomenon indicates that personal branding on social media is not solely determined by self-representation strategies, but also by

processes of public perception influenced by experiences, values, biases, and evolving social contexts.

Based on this phenomenon, this study employs Stuart Hall's reception theory as the primary theoretical framework to understand the positions of netizens in accepting, negotiating, or rejecting Jennifer Coppen's personal branding on TikTok. This theory is utilized because netizens' comments not only reflect spontaneous responses but also reveal active meaning-making processes toward the image Jennifer presents. In addition, this study applies Peter Montoya's *Eight Laws of Personal Branding* concept as the second primary theoretical framework to examine the elements of Jennifer Coppen's image, particularly regarding personality, visibility, image unity, persistence, and goodwill.

METHOD

This study employed a qualitative method with a narrative analysis approach to understand the dynamics of netizens' perceptions toward Jennifer Coppen's personal branding on TikTok. This approach was chosen because the research does not focus on statistical measurement of comments, but rather on interpreting meanings, emotions, support, criticism, and social judgments emerging in digital interactions. Netizens' comments are understood as digital narratives containing stories, conflicts, experiences, and social messages related to the transformation of Jennifer Coppen's image across different phases of her life. Narrative analysis was applied to interpret how audiences construct meaning toward public figures through communication on social media (Creswell, 2014; Riessman, 2008; Waruwu, 2024; Cropley, 2022).

The research was conducted on the TikTok platform, with the primary data sources consisting of Jennifer Coppen's uploads and netizens' comments on the account @jennifer.coppen during the period from May 2023 to August 2025. The research focus was divided into three life phases: the phase of pregnancy disclosure before marriage, the phase of family life until the loss of her partner, and the phase of introducing a new partner to the public sphere. The research corpus was selected purposively and consisted of nine TikTok videos with a total of 72 netizen comments considered representative in illustrating public support, empathy, criticism, and disappointment toward Jennifer Coppen's personal branding. Content selection also considered the level of interaction and moments of public attention through Google Trends to ensure that the analyzed data were relevant to the dynamics of public opinion in the digital sphere (Resi, 2022; Nawaf, 2025).

Data collection techniques were conducted through digital observation, documentation of netizens' comments and interactions, documentation of TikTok content, and identification of moments of public attention using Google Trends. Data analysis employed a narrative analysis approach consisting of narrative identification, theme categorization, story structure analysis, meaning interpretation, and conclusion drawing. This study also utilized Stuart Hall's reception theory to identify the meaning-making positions of netizens and Peter Montoya's personal branding concept to examine the image elements of Jennifer Coppen reflected in netizens' comments. Through this approach, the study is able to explain how public perception

is formed, negotiated, and dynamically transformed through digital interactions on TikTok (Krippendorff, 2018; Kozinets, 2015; Qomaruddin & Sa'diyah, 2024; Ming Ho et al., 2024; Mudianto et al., 2025).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Jennifer Coppen's TikTok Content

Table 1. Characteristics of Jennifer Coppen's TikTok Content

Content Type	Content Example	Description of Content
Daily life content (<i>a day in my life, vlog, get ready with me</i>)		Displays Jennifer's daily activities, such as morning routines, eating, traveling, working, taking care of her child, or spending time with her partner and family.
Personal sharing content		Presents Jennifer's expressions of feelings, thoughts, guilt, gratitude, sadness, or explanations regarding the situations she is experiencing. This type of content usually appears in the form of direct-to-camera videos or relatively long captions.
Photo slide content		Displays a collection of photos featuring her child, family, partner, vacations, or particular

		<p>moments in Jennifer's life.</p>
<p>Endorsement or promotional content</p>		<p>Displays promotional content related to brand collaborations or Jennifer's businesses, such as <i>Jennskin</i> and <i>Chewy Dessert</i>. Jennifer typically presents this content in a manner that remains consistent with the character of her personal account.</p>
<p>Light entertainment and personal appearance content</p>		<p>Displays lip-sync videos, the use of trending sounds, and uploads highlighting Jennifer's appearance, such as outfits and makeup.</p>

The content on Jennifer Coppen’s TikTok account is predominantly centered on daily activities, emotional expression, visual documentation, and product promotion presented in a personal manner, thereby creating a sense of closeness with the audience. Jennifer also consistently displays her emotional side through personal sharing content and visual uploads portraying her personal life, family, and social relationships. On the other hand, commercial activities such as endorsements and business promotions remain integrated with the personal character of her account, making them appear as a natural part of her everyday life rather than as separate commercial content. The combination of personal, emotional, light entertainment, and business-related content demonstrates that Jennifer Coppen’s TikTok account is constructed as a dynamic space of self-representation that remains closely connected to the public.

Jennifer Coppen’s personal branding on TikTok is formed through an image that is approachable, straightforward, protective, resilient, and professional in her interactions with the audience. Her approachable image can be seen in her closeness with netizens through casual comment replies and the use of terms of address such as “Till” and “mamari,” which reflect an emotional connection with her followers. In addition, Jennifer also appears as a straightforward and protective figure through her firm responses to negative comments, particularly those concerning Kamari, thereby demonstrating a clear boundary between criticism directed at herself and criticism directed at her child. Meanwhile, the image of resilience and professionalism is constructed through narratives from netizens who perceive Jennifer as a strong mother following the loss of her partner, as well as through her business activities and promotional content that remain naturally integrated with the character of her personal account.

Data Presentation

This section presents the dynamics of netizens’ perceptions of Jennifer Coppen’s personal branding on TikTok through three different phases of her life in

order to more clearly identify shifts in the tendencies of public responses. The selection of uploads was conducted purposively based on the relevance of the context of Jennifer Coppen’s life, the high level of interaction generated by the uploads, and the support of Google Trends data to ensure that the selected uploads had received broad public attention. The selected comments were then categorized according to the tendencies of netizens’ responses, such as criticism, support, empathy, and appreciation, thereby illustrating the evolving patterns of public perception in each phase of Jennifer Coppen’s life.

Initial Phase: Netizens’ Perceptions of the Out-of-Wedlock Pregnancy Case

The initial phase in this study refers to the period when Jennifer Coppen first became the focus of public attention after news of her pregnancy became widely discussed on social media. During this period, netizens’ attention toward Jennifer Coppen increased significantly, as reflected in the large amount of interaction appearing on her TikTok uploads. This phase is important because it marks the stage at which the comment section began to display various responses from netizens toward Jennifer Coppen as a public figure.

The researcher focused the presentation of data in the initial phase on three TikTok uploads published by Jennifer Coppen in May 2023. These uploads were selected because May represented a period of heightened public attention toward Jennifer Coppen, and the study utilized Google Trends to help identify moments of intensified public attention during a particular period. The data presented in this section illustrate netizens’ responses at a time when Jennifer Coppen’s name was being widely discussed.

1. First Post

Table 2. Jennifer Coppen’s Upload in the First Post of the First Phase

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Criticism	“Marriage is not a private matter, sis... the whole world should know so that misunderstandings and slander do not arise.”
		“Basically, marital status or marriage news is not something private, guys...”
		“Wouldn’t marriage actually be much better and prevent people from questioning things?”
	Condemnation	“INDONESIA IS A COUNTRY THAT HAS NORMS!”
		“I really do not understand anymore. It is truly the end times.”

	Disappointment	“Jenn, this is not a foreign country.”
	Support	“Until this moment, she is still a good woman and mother because she chose to keep her baby 😊”
		“I admire her even more because she is ready to face everything, especially when nowadays many babies are abandoned.”

The comments on the first upload were distributed across the categories of criticism, condemnation, disappointment, and support, reflecting the diverse responses of netizens toward Jennifer Coppen. Most criticisms focused on Jennifer’s statement regarding the privacy of marriage, while condemnatory comments appeared more direct and emotional through short statements expressing anger and referring to social norms in Indonesia. Expressions of disappointment emerged through comments emphasizing that Jennifer’s situation was perceived as inconsistent with prevailing social values. Meanwhile, supportive comments highlighted empathy and appreciation for Jennifer’s sense of responsibility as an expectant mother. The differences in language style across each category demonstrate that, from the outset, the comment section had become a space for negotiation between moral judgment, social criticism, and emotional support directed toward Jennifer Coppen.

2. Second Post

Table 3. Jennifer Coppen’s Upload in the Second Post of the First Phase

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Criticism	“This is why learning religious values is important 😞 not that I am already perfect, just to remind us :)”
		“Things like this seem so normalized nowadays, it is honestly scary 😭”
	Condemnation	“What can you do when someone already lives by the principle of ‘I can do whatever I want?’”
		“Not surprising though, her lifestyle has always seemed too free.”
	Disappointment	“Really disappointed, Till. Why did you have to get pregnant first?”

		“Quite disappointed, especially because it was announced publicly like this.”
	Support	“As human beings, we can take the good and leave the bad. After all, the child is not at fault because children cannot choose their parents.”
		“In the end, whatever happens is their shared responsibility. We can only pray for the best for them and for our own families.”

The comments on the second upload were distributed across the categories of criticism, condemnation, disappointment, and support, with a stronger emotional tone compared to the previous upload. Criticism and condemnatory comments largely focused on Jennifer Coppen’s lifestyle and pregnancy situation, which were perceived as inconsistent with prevailing social values. Meanwhile, comments expressing disappointment reflected an emotional distance between netizens and Jennifer through expressions of disappointment, concern, and anxiety. On the other hand, supportive comments emphasized humanity, responsibility, and prayers for Jennifer and Dali, making the comment section on this upload not only a space for moral judgment, but also a space for netizens’ emotional expression regarding the situation.

3. Third Post

Table 4. Jennifer Coppen’s Upload in the Third Post of the First Phase

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Criticism	“Normalizing something that is clearly wrong, and her parents do not seem to respond to it at all.”
		“It is enough to support her sense of responsibility, but not her free behavior.”
	Condemnation	“Justifying something that is obviously wrong and defending herself because of her achievements 😏”

		“Whoever supports someone in wrongdoing becomes part of that person and will be with them in the afterlife.”
	Disappointment	“I used to be a fan, but not anymore 😞”
		“As a public figure, she should set a good example, especially because children might imitate her.”
	Support	“Let people say whatever they want, the important thing is that Kak Jeni is truly kind. Stay healthy and may your blessings continue to increase.”
“Till, do not think too much about the comments. Just be yourself, YOU ARE AMAZING ❤️❤️”		

The comments on the third upload were also distributed across the categories of criticism, condemnation, disappointment, and support. Critical comments emphasized concerns regarding the normalization of behavior considered inappropriate, while condemnatory comments appeared more assertive by associating support for Jennifer with moral deviation. Expressions of disappointment reflected the shifting perceptions of several followers who felt that Jennifer, as a public figure, should serve as a positive role model for the public, particularly for younger audiences. In contrast, supportive comments highlighted emotional encouragement and appreciation for Jennifer’s personal character. The interaction patterns within this comment section indicate that public perception of Jennifer Coppen during the first phase was shaped through tensions between moral values, expectations toward public figures, and emotional solidarity from her supporters..

Second Phase: Netizens’ Perceptions during the Family Life Phase and the Loss of a Partner

The second phase in this study refers to the period when Jennifer Coppen appeared as a wife, mother, and part of a family with Dali Wassink, resulting in uploads that predominantly portrayed family life, her role as a mother, and the grieving period following the loss of her partner. Through three TikTok uploads representing moments of marriage, everyday life as a mother, and the period after Dali’s passing, the researcher found that netizens’ responses during this phase experienced a shift from the dominance of condemnatory comments toward

responses characterized more by support, empathy, appreciation, and recognition of Jennifer as a mother.

1. First Post

Table 5. Jennifer Coppen’s Upload in the First Post of the Second Phase

Postingan	Category	Comment Content
	Support	<p>“Do not pay attention to what people say. Keep living the best version of yourself, Till, and take responsibility for what is already in front of you ❤️”</p>
		<p>SO HAPPY FOR YOUUU GUYS 😭😭😭😭👉❤️❤️❤️ CONGRATULATIONS 😭😭😭😭👉👉👉</p>
	Empathy	<p>“Regardless of the mistakes she may have made, she is still a great mother and woman.”</p>
		<p>“I do not want to judge other people’s lives because only Allah is the Most Just Judge 😞 Till, whatever happens, may Allah forgive all of our sins, and please stay strong.”</p>
	Appreciation	<p>Till, I am proud of you. After going through so many hardships in your life before, now you have succeeded in becoming a great mother 🍀🍀”</p>
		<p>“You are truly amazing, Till. You made mistakes, but you knew how to make things right. I may be nobody, but I truly admire you 😊”</p>
Criticism	<p>“Is this an out-of-wedlock child?”</p>	
	<p>“Back then, why was it so difficult to simply say, ‘Yes, I got pregnant</p>	

		before marriage’? Instead, it just created unnecessary drama 🙏”
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The comments on this upload were predominantly characterized by empathy and appreciation, indicating that some netizens had begun to accept Jennifer Coppen’s circumstances as a mother and a woman who had gone through many life experiences. Netizens expressed support in a warmer and more emotional tone, portraying Jennifer as a strong and admirable figure who deserved appreciation for the struggles she had endured. Although criticism still appeared, particularly regarding her pregnancy before marriage and her attitude during the previous phase, such comments no longer dominated the discussion as they had in the initial phase. Overall, the language used by netizens in this upload reflects a shift toward perceptions that are more positive, emotional, and appreciative of Jennifer Coppen.

2. Second Post

Table 6. Jennifer Coppen’s Upload in the Second Post of the Second Phase

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Support	“No one is allowed to disturb this happy family.”
		“Enjoy your timeeeee!!!! Thank you for being such a good mother ❤️”
		“AAAA DON’T FEEL BAD MAMA JENN!! A mama deserves a happy time too. Hope you have fun and keep taking care of your health for Kamari as well!!”
	Empathy	“It’s okay, Mama. You deserve the trip after everything you have been through, and it is okay to take some rest. All mothers deserve it ❤️”
		“It’s okay, Mama. You also need some me time occasionally. Do not feel like a bad mom, you are a good mom, Till.”
		“Kamari also looks happy even when left behind. She surely understands that her mother also needs healing because she must be very exhausted 😊”

	Appreciation	“Jennifer is still so young, yet she has already become an extraordinary mother 👍👍👍👍”
		“Mama Kamari is very mature in taking care of Kamari, even though she is still very young.”

Appreciative comments on this upload were primarily directed toward Jennifer’s young age despite already undertaking the role of a mother. Statements such as “Jennifer is still so young, yet she has already become an extraordinary mother” and “Mama Kamari is very mature” indicate that netizens acknowledged Jennifer’s maturity in taking care of her child. The use of the 👍👍👍👍 emojis in one of the comments further emphasized the admiration expressed by the commenter.

Compared to the first upload in this phase, the comments on the second post appeared softer and more personal. Netizens no longer focused heavily on Jennifer’s past, but instead paid greater attention to her position as a mother and a young woman carrying out family responsibilities. The comment section on the second upload appeared more supportive and reflected a more positive image of Jennifer.

3. Third Post

Table 7. Jennifer Copen’s Upload in the Third Post of the Second Phase

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Empathy	“Mamari looks happy in front of her child even though her heart is deeply broken. Mamari is truly so strong 😔”
		“Mama Kamari, you are amazing and strong. Oh God, it hurts even for us watching this 💔💔 It must feel so painful when you return home, especially to the room where you both slept together every day and shared stories every night 💔”
		“Kamari and Jennifer, may you always be the happiest daughter and mother. I am proud of you, Jenn, because you can still smile in front of Kamari even though your heart is broken 🍷”

	Support	“I know you were given this trial because you are strong enough to get through it, even though it is very difficult. Stay strong, Mama Kamari. I know you will probably read this 😊😊”
		“Jen, God has given you extraordinary pain, but He has also prepared the remedy 🥹❤️ Kamari is an extraordinary blessing, Jen 🥹🙏 She is healthy, beautiful, smart, and even able to bring happiness to many people 🥹🙏”
		“Mamariiii, that is only in Bali. Outside Bali, there are still so many people who love you both 🥹🥹❤️❤️ Sending a big hug from all of us outside Bali, Mamariiii ☐”
	Appreciation	“And thank you to Mamari for teaching all of us the importance of finding a good man for the future of our children in the next generation. Strong women like Mamari truly deserve appreciation ☐👉”
		“Wow, Jennifer is truly amazing for being this strong. I am already crying just watching Kamari’s videos, so I cannot imagine how it feels seeing Kamari directly 🥹🥹🥹 Thank you, Jen, for staying this strong for Kamari. We love you ❤️❤️❤”

The comments on the third upload were predominantly characterized by empathy, support, and appreciation, positioning Jennifer Copen as a mother who continued to remain strong amid a period of grief. Many netizens expressed prayers, encouragement, and deep sympathy toward Jennifer and Kamari, causing the comment section to be filled with emotional expressions and a sense of personal closeness. In addition, appreciation toward Jennifer was directed not only at her resilience, but also at her image as a mother figure who was perceived as providing lessons and inspiration for others. These findings indicate that during the second

phase, netizens' perceptions of Jennifer Coppen underwent a significant transformation, shifting from predominantly condemnatory responses toward support, empathy, and recognition of her life struggles.

Third Phase: Netizens' Perceptions of Jennifer Coppen's Introduction of a New Partner

The third phase of this study refers to the period when Jennifer Coppen began publicly showing her closeness with a new partner, which generated sharper responses from netizens who frequently associated her recent uploads with the image and statements she had expressed during previous phases. Through three TikTok uploads with different contexts, namely vacations with her new partner, personal uploads, and endorsement content, the researcher found that comments during this phase were dominated by criticism, condemnation, and disappointment, although a small number of netizens continued to express support for Jennifer Coppen.

1. First Post

Figure 2. Jennifer Coppen's Statement during the Mourning Period

Following the appearance of this upload, the comment section was immediately filled with responses that not only focused on Jennifer's new relationship, but also evaluated the consistency between her past statements and her current actions. Some netizens expressed criticism, condemnation, and disappointment by referring back to statements previously made by Jennifer that they had heard or read. Nevertheless, several netizens continued to provide support and argued that Jennifer had the right to live her own life.

Based on Table 8 below, the comments on the first post were largely dominated by criticism, condemnation, and disappointment. The criticism expressed did not merely focus on the presence of Justin Hubner, but also directly referred to Jennifer's previous statements. Comments such as "from the beginning, do not say that you would never marry again" and "she was the one who previously said not to matchmake her with anyone" demonstrate that netizens brought Jennifer's past statements back into discussion within this upload.

Table 8. Jennifer Coppen’s Upload in the First Post of the Third Phase

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Criticism	“I do not want to insult her, but honestly it would have been better if from the beginning she had not said that she would never get married again. It gives a certain impression.”
	Criticism	“The problem is that she was the one who previously said not to matchmake her with anyone, but later when criticized she brings up anxiety and starts crying. What netizens actually mean is that her husband has not even been gone for a year, so she should not show too openly that she is already in love with Justin.”
	Condemnation	“Both of them seem equally desperate for validation 😭👉”
	Disappointment	“Where are those beautiful words now, ‘No one can replace Dali and I will never marry again’ 😭 It suddenly feels like she forgot all those beautiful statements 😊”
	Disappointment	“Back then during the girls’ trip to Japan, she said she could not bear to leave Kamari until Dali told her to bring Kamari along. So how is she suddenly able to leave Kamari now? 😊”
	Disappointment	“It seems like we were only fans of Kamari after all 😭🙏”
	Support	“Just live your life in whatever way makes you happy, Till. Do not

		listen too much to what people say 😞”

The comments on the first upload in the third phase were dominated by condemnation and disappointment that not only evaluated Jennifer Coppen’s situation, but also attacked her personal character through cynical tones and mockery reinforced by the use of emojis. Many netizens associated the upload with Jennifer’s previous statements regarding Dali and Kamari, resulting in comments that reflected disappointment toward the perceived inconsistency between her words, actions, and the image she had previously constructed. Nevertheless, some netizens continued to express support by emphasizing that Jennifer had the right to move forward with her life and pursue her own happiness.

2. Second Post

Table 9. Jennifer Coppen’s Upload in the Second Post of the Third Phase

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Criticism	“It is up to you who you are with, but do not cross the line. Just a reminder. Kamari is still very young, so you should learn from past experiences.”
	Criticism	“It is up to you who you are with, but do not cross the line. Just a reminder. Kamari is still very young, so you should learn from past experiences.”
	Criticism	“Jennifer herself is the reason people think negatively about her because her words do not match reality 😞 but whatever.”
	Condemnation	“Just watch, she often ends up contradicting her own statements. Let us see how this current relationship ends.”
	Condemnation	“Netizens are not exaggerating. They are only repeating her own words as a reminder of what she previously said.”

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Disappointment	“Turns out it was pointless for me to cry over her back then.”
	Disappointment	“Didn’t she say she wanted to leave social media? 😊”
	Support	“You deserve happiness with Kamari, Jen. Hopefully you will find a partner who can make both of you happy. Do not listen to your haters.”

The comments on the second upload were still dominated by criticism, condemnation, and disappointment, particularly focusing on the inconsistency between Jennifer Coppen’s previous statements and her current actions. The phrase “contradicting her own words” repeatedly appeared as a form of condemnation, emphasizing that netizens perceived Jennifer as inconsistent in constructing her public image. Netizens’ disappointment was also evident in comments linking the upload to their emotional experiences during the previous phase, indicating that the responses were not merely critical, but also personal and emotional. Nevertheless, some netizens continued to express support by emphasizing that Jennifer had the right to move on with her life and seek happiness together with Kamari.

3. Third Post

Table 10. Jennifer Coppen’s Upload in the Third Post of the Third Phase

Post	Category	Comment Content
	Criticism	“Good deeds should be kept private, yet your immoral actions are displayed publicly?”
	Criticism	“FOR ONCE, THERE ARE NO REPLIES TO THE COMMENTS. Usually, whenever someone comments, she immediately responds angrily and aggressively 😊👉”
	Condemnation	“If it were not for Kamari, I would not even know who this person is 😊”

	Condemnation	“I want to leave a negative comment but I am afraid of getting reported 😞🙅”
	Condemnation	“I used Jennifer’s deodorant and it caused irritation, guys. It did not suit me.”
	Condemnation	“Only sensible people do not idolize this person.”
	Disappointment	“She likes commenting on other people, but she really cannot handle being commented on herself hahaha.”
	Support	“It’s okay, Till, be happyyyy. Your happiness does not hurt anyone, and in fact your happiness makes Kamari and your family happy too. You deserve to be happy 🧡🧡🧡🧡”

Netizens’ comments on the third upload were dominated by condemnation and disappointment that no longer focused on the endorsement video itself, but rather on Jennifer Coppen’s overall public image. Some netizens perceived Jennifer as inconsistent in responding to public comments, while the use of emojis and cynical expressions strengthened the tone of criticism and dislike directed toward her. Nevertheless, several supportive comments continued to appear, emphasizing that Jennifer had the right to feel happy and was not harming anyone else. These findings indicate that netizens’ perceptions of Jennifer during this phase had become deeply attached to her public persona, causing her personal life and personal branding to continue influencing various types of uploads, including commercial content that did not directly discuss her new relationship.

Discussion

This study interprets netizens’ comments on TikTok as digital narratives containing judgments, emotions, social values, and processes of meaning negotiation regarding Jennifer Coppen’s personal branding. By applying Stuart Hall’s reception theory and Peter Montoya’s concept of the *eight laws of personal branding*, this study demonstrates that netizens’ reception of Jennifer Coppen changed according to the life contexts presented, ranging from the phase of pregnancy before marriage, family life and the loss of a partner, to the emergence of a new partner. In the first phase, netizens’ comments were dominated by narratives of morality that

positioned Jennifer as a public figure perceived to violate social norms, whereas in the second phase public perception shifted toward narratives of empathy that viewed Jennifer as a resilient mother and woman facing grief. However, in the third phase, reception became divided once again because some netizens supported Jennifer's right to move forward with her life, while others questioned the consistency of the image she had previously established.

The findings reveal that Jennifer Coppen's personal branding on TikTok was not entirely under her own control, but was continuously negotiated through interactions and conversations among netizens within digital spaces. TikTok, as an algorithmic platform, intensified these dynamics because comments, support, criticism, and debates among netizens formed a collective narrative flow that influenced public perceptions of Jennifer. This study also demonstrates that the image of female public figures on social media is strongly influenced by social expectations, moral values, emotional relationships, and contextual events developing within society. Therefore, personal branding on TikTok should not merely be understood as a strategy for constructing a positive image, but rather as a social process that continuously changes through reception, interaction, and the negotiation of meaning between public figures and digital audiences.

CONCLUSION

This study found that netizens' perceptions of Jennifer Coppen's personal branding on TikTok were dynamically constructed through digital narratives containing criticism, empathy, support, and social judgments throughout each phase of her life. During the phase of revealing pregnancy before marriage, netizens' reception was dominated by *negotiated reading* and *oppositional reading*, as many comments perceived Jennifer's actions as inconsistent with prevailing social norms, although some still expressed empathy toward her as an expectant mother. These perceptions later shifted during the phase of family life and the loss of her partner, when Jennifer was more widely perceived as a resilient young mother, resulting in responses dominated by support, sympathy, and *dominant-hegemonic reading*. However, during the phase of introducing a new partner, netizens' perceptions became divided once again because Jennifer's uploads were interpreted in relation to the previous narratives of grief. This demonstrates that the personal branding of public figures on social media is fluctuating in nature and continuously negotiated through audience responses and the dynamics of digital platforms.

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